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Could Microplastic Clean Our Ocean?

Review on The Possibility of The Biodegradation of Adsorbed Pollutants by Microorganisms Loaded on Microplastics

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Abstract: A large number of studies have reported the potential risks of microplastics (MPs) in the global water environment. Due to its high specific surface area and hydrophobicity, MPs can adsorb and accumulate many kinds of pollutants in the marine environment, including heavy metals and persistent organic pollutants (POPs). At the same time, when MPs enter the natural water, microorganisms will colonize its surface and form biofilms. Previous studies have focused on the threat of MPs as carriers of pollutants and special microbial communities in the food chain, but have not assessed the microbial degradation potential to the pollutants. This paper reviews the interaction of biofilms on MPs with adsorbed pollutants and microorganisms in the process of MP migration in the environment. Our main focus is to ask specifically the degradation ability of special kinds of microorganisms to typical pollutants on MPs. After analyzing the degradation potential in the life cycle of microplastics, we think that microplastics may indeed become a platform for specific microbial community degradation of related harmful pollutants.

Keywords: microplastic, persistent organic pollutant, biofilm, degradation

34 1. Introduction

35 Marine litter or anthropogenic marine debris, particularly from plastics, is amongst the most
36 pervasive pollution problems affecting the marine environment globally.[1] It is estimated that
37 4.6 - 12.7 million tons plastics are added yearly from land-based sources into the ocean, most
38 of which comes from densely populated coastlines and river inputs.[2] Microplastic (MP) is
39 defined as plastic fragments with a particle size less than 5 mm, which is the most abundant
40 form of plastic in the ocean.[3] Microplastics are divided into two categories according to their
41 sources. The primary MPs refer to the artificially produced small particles used in the industrial
42 production, cosmetics and medical supplies[4], and the secondary MPs refers to the plastic
43 particles that have broken off or degraded from large-scale plastic fragments by current,
44 ultraviolet rays, wind force, etc.[5] Currently, Microplastics have been found all over the world,
45 from surface water to deep-sea sediments, as well as in freshwater systems and even remote ice
46 cores in the Arctic. [6] For example, the surface water in the Northwest Pacific Ocean is widely
47 polluted by microplastics, with a concentration range of 640 - 42000 items/km². [7] Due to its
48 ubiquitous existence and the difficulty of degradation as polymers, the environmental risks of
49 microplastics have become an important research area.

50 Microplastics are known to sorb organic and metallic contaminants from surrounding
51 water.[8] Due to the hydrophobic and lipophilic[9] surface, microplastics can highly adsorb and
52 concentrate hydrophobic organic compounds (HOCs), of which most are persistent organic
53 Pollutants (POPs)[10], such as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), organochlorine
54 pesticides, polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs).
55 [11] The concentration of some POPs attached to MPs can reach 10,000 ng/g, which is several
56 orders of magnitude higher than that in the surrounding environment.[10] POPs are considered
57 to be the most persistent man-made organic compounds introduced into the environment and
58 are widely distributed in the global marine environment. These pollutants have a wide range of
59 chronic effects, including endocrine interference, mutagenicity and carcinogenicity. The
60 accumulation of plastics and related PCBs and PAHs in the marine food web has been
61 proved[12]. In addition to organic pollutants, heavy metals have also been shown to accumulate
62 on the surface of microplastics, including Zn, Cu and other poisonous metals.[13]

63 At the same time, microplastics floating in the ocean will quickly be colonized by
64 microorganisms. Since the earliest study of bacteria on the surface of plastic spherules in
65 1972,[14] a large number of studies have been carried out to investigate the colonization of
66 various microorganisms in the marine environment on the surface of microplastics and their
67 effects on the environmental behavior of MPs.[15] Aggregate of microorganisms in which cells
68 that are frequently embedded within a self-produced matrix of extracellular polymeric
69 substance (EPS) adhere to each other and to a surface forming a biofilm. [16]Biofilms can form
70 rapidly on all kinds of microplastics in a few weeks, and make microplastics less hydrophobic
71 and easier to float to meet and adsorb other pollutants.[17] Certain bacterial groups belonging

72 to the phyla Proteobacteria, Bacteroidetes, Firmicutes, and Cyanobacteria appear to be enriched
 73 on plastic more often than others, in which some class of bacteria have been proven to have the
 74 ability to degrade PAHs and even polymers themselves.[15]

75 When studying the environmental risk of MPs, a large number of mainstream literatures
 76 regard microplastics as the carrier of hazardous pollutants and harmful microorganisms, and a
 77 few voices call for attention to the "real risk" of microplastics. The uptake of microplastic by
 78 lugworms, mussels, amphipods, barnacles, sea cucumbers, and fish has been described, but
 79 negative biological effects of microplastic have not yet been determined[18], and the
 80 concentration of MPs used in the experiment is often much higher than that in the actual
 81 environment.[19] Moreover, a considerable number of studies have shown that plastics are
 82 unlikely to increase the bioaccumulation of POPs in organisms.[20] Therefore, we propose a
 83 new perspective to reconsider the interaction between microplastics as harmful pollutants and
 84 microbial carriers.

85 Based on the characteristics of MPs introduced so far, we raise the possibility that MPs
 86 could facilitate the degradation of pollutants adsorbed to it by the biofilm on its surface as the
 87 interactions in the lifecycle of MPs shown in Figure 1. MPs may also be capable to decrease
 88 the concentration of POPs in water and decrease the bioavailability of these contaminants to
 89 marine species.[21] The microorganisms colonized on the MPs may also have the potential to
 90 degrade the pollutants.[22] Generally speaking, there are also a large number of bacteria that
 91 can degrade pollutants on microplastics in seawater.[23] Studies have shown that biofilms can
 92 help the interaction between metals and plastics and metals could potentially be used as
 93 nutrients by cells in the biofilm.[24] Therefore, if MPs provide colonizable habitats, the biofilm
 94 on the surface of MPs may become a place for bacteria to degrade pollutants, and microplastic
 95 may also serve as a carrier for enriching pollutants and carrying biofilm in its life cycle. These
 96 facts lead us to rethink the real ecological impact of MPs and their interaction with microbial
 97 communities and pollutants during their life cycle.

98 Figure. 1 Interaction of microplastics with microorganisms and pollutants in their life cycle
 99

100 In the following we summarize the types, distribution and concentration of pollutants
101 adsorbed by MPs, the process of biofilm formation on the surface of MPs and the types of
102 bacteria in the biofilm. The existing literature about the degradation capacity of some of the
103 bacteria, the degradation potential of different substances, and the interaction between
104 microbial colonization and pollutant adsorption are analyzed. We found the several kinds of
105 bacteria with degradation capacities overlap with bacteria that are found on MPs and we try to
106 analysis the changes in pollutants and bacterial community composition during the aging of
107 plastic. It is concluded that in the whole life cycle of MPs, they absorb a large number of
108 pollutants, colonized by microorganisms, forming biofilms in which there are bacteria that can
109 degrade pollutants, which makes MPs ideal to become platforms of pollutant degradation.

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111 **2. Pollutants Adsorbed by Microplastics**

112 In order to evaluate the degradation potential, first we need to determine the types and
113 concentrations of pollutants adsorbed on the surface of the microplastics, as well as their
114 distribution areas. This part analyzes the current research on the surface pollutants of
115 microplastics specially on organic pollutants and inorganic pollutants (heavy metals), and why
116 we should pay attention to whether these pollutants can be degraded.

117 **2.1 Organic Pollutants**

118 When MPs enter the aquatic environment, because of their high specific surface area,
119 hydrophobicity, polarity and special functional groups of the polymer, they will absorb the
120 hydrophobic organic pollutants in the surrounding environment. A variety of POPs have been
121 proven to be adsorbed on the surface of microplastics, and could have high concentrations.[25]
122 Guo et al. Summarized the global organic pollutant concentration (PAHs, PCBs, HCHs and
123 DDTs) mapping reported in the literature as shown in Figure 2.[26] Strikingly, in the coastal
124 urban areas of East Asia, South America and North America, the concentrations of PAH and
125 PCB on the microplastics are as high as > 5000 ng/g. The difference in distribution indicates
126 that the pollutants adsorbed by the microplastics are closely related to the geographical areas.
127 PAHs have complex aromatic structure, high resonance energy and limited bioavailability.
128 Incomplete combustion of carbon containing substances and crude oil leakage are the main
129 sources of PAH.[23] PCB is a group of chlorinated organic substances, which widely appears
130 in various industrial products.[27] These two kinds of substances are widespread pollutants in
131 the environment, known for their highly toxic and wide range of chronic effects. Because of
132 their chemical stability, they are persistent in the environment and are one of the most
133 prominent and widespread environmental pollutants, which are likely to accumulate through
134 the food chain and reach aquatic organisms, fish and human bodies.[27] Specific microbial
135 degradation is the only way to degrade them under natural conditions.[28] Therefore, the

136 microplastics enriched with POPs have strong ecological risks, and it is very important to know
 137 whether they can be degraded by microorganisms.

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Figure. 2 Average concentration ranges of organic pollutants on microplastics. [26]

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Apart from traditional pollutants, microplastics can also adsorb emerging contaminants (ECs) which have raised increasing attention. One of them is perfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), which is highly stable and widely distributed in the environment, which is related to a variety of toxic effects. MPs with aging and smaller particle size can increase the adsorption capacity.[29] A recent study demonstrated the strong adsorption of ciprofloxacin (CIP) on the aged PVC and PS surfaces, which is a representative pharmaceuticals and personal care products (PPCP).[30] This means that we need to consider the increasing adsorption of pollutants and the potential adsorption of more kinds of pollutants with the aging process of plastics. This will also be analyzed in the subsequent interaction with biofilm.

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Understanding how microplastics absorb these pollutants will help us predict the impact of biofilm on this process later. The main interaction mechanism between MPs and organic pollutants included partition, hydrogen bonding, cation exchange, π - π interactions and electrostatic attraction,[30] which enabled them to adsorb a lot kinds of organic molecules with different functional groups. With the aging and wear of microplastics, more oxygen-containing functional groups appear on the surface, which makes the adsorption of hydrophilic organic pollutants also possible.

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2.2 Inorganic Pollutants

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Recent studies[31] have shown that microplastics also have a high affinity for heavy metals, and so can rapidly absorb the heavy metals released by nearby pollution sources. Heavy metals are a very important pollutant which have aroused increasing attention because of the wide

161 range of pollution and ecological risk. Existing studies have found complex metal mixtures on
162 the most common plastic debris in the ocean, and have little to do with the type of polymer[32],
163 so the we didn't consider types of plastic in the discussion.

164 The concentration of heavy metals adsorbed by microplastics varies greatly according to
165 different species and locations. The review of Guo et al. summarized the average concentration
166 ranges of metals on microplastics, indicating that at low initial concentration ($< 20 \mu\text{g/L}$), the
167 absorption range of Ag, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Hg, Ni, Pb and Zn by microplastics is from 0.0004 to
168 $2.78 \mu\text{g/g}$, while in some high pollution areas, such as near the river mouth and pollution sources,
169 the concentration of Zn and Cu can reach thousands of $\mu\text{g/g}$. [26]

170 The adsorption of heavy metals by microplastics has also been shown to be affected by the
171 aging of plastics and the biofilm on the surface. Dennis et al. showed that copper and zinc
172 leached from antifouling coatings of ship hull will be adsorbed by the original aged polystyrene
173 (PS) and polyvinyl chloride (PVC) fragments in sea water, and analyzed the distribution
174 coefficients of adsorbed Cu by adsorption kinetics. [33] Due to photooxidation weathering,
175 biofilm accumulation and chemical hydriding precipitation, the reactivity of aged plastic
176 particles can be increased, so that metal ions can be more adsorbed from the water column. [34]
177 Wang et al. verified that under the condition of ultraviolet aging, the adsorption capacity of pet
178 microplastics to copper and zinc ions in the water environment can reach $200\mu\text{g/g}$, which is
179 caused by the increase of specific surface area and the complexation capacity of oxygen-
180 containing functional groups to metal ions. [35] Another study showed that the cumulative
181 concentration of Cr, Cu, Co and Pb on PE, PP, PS and PVC in seawater could reach 2 mg/L in
182 5 days, and the presence of organic matter would increase the adsorption of lead and chromium
183 on plastics. [36] In these works, Freundlich and Langmuir isotherms are both used to describe
184 the adsorption of metals on microplastics, indicating that this is a complex mechanism. Some
185 studies thought that metal accumulation in microplastics is more dependent on biofilm
186 mediated, [32] So we can think that the biofilm may have a complex role in the process of metal
187 adsorption.

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189 **3. Biofilm and Microbe Species on MPs**

190 In order to evaluate whether microorganisms on the surface of MPs can degrade pollutants,
191 understanding the formation process of biofilm on the surface of MPs can help to understand
192 the principle of microbial survival. Furthermore, by analyzing which microbial species colonize
193 MPs, we will later be able to conclude whether these species overlap with pollutant degrading
194 species. And hence, whether or not to expect microbial degradation of pollutants on MPs.

195 **3.1 The Formation Process of Biofilm on the Surface of Microplastics**

196 Macro/meso and microplastics can generally act as physical hosts for a variety of surface
197 attached phytoplankton, bacteria and invertebrates. [37] It is a common phenomenon in aquatic

198 ecosystem that microorganisms tend to attach to organic and inorganic particles. For granular
199 substrates, even if they are not rich in organic nutrients, they will accelerate the growth of
200 attached microorganisms.[38] Biofilms are phylogenetic and functionally diverse communities
201 of bacteria, algae, protozoa, and fungi, collectively referred to as microbial aggregates, and are
202 mainly composed of EPS. EPS plays an important role in the interaction of biofilm and
203 pollutants. [39]

204 According to the environment, microorganisms can stimulate the production of
205 corresponding enzymes, which is also the basis of microbial degradation of pollutants. Within
206 a few seconds after the release of microplastics into the water environment, the surface of
207 microplastics has formed a regulating layer or membrane of organic and inorganic substances
208 through adsorption.[40] This is the first step of microbial attachment on the MPs. As a function
209 of existing matrix and organism, the regulatory membrane can change specific surface
210 characteristics of materials and affect colonization population.[37] The first coating promotes
211 the adhesion of other microorganisms to form more complex biofilms, a self-generating matrix
212 of extracellular organics that provides mechanical stability, mediates the adhesion of
213 microorganisms to the surface, and allows for the insertion of extracellular enzyme microbial
214 metabolism.[41]

215 At the beginning of the life cycle of microplastics, there is enough time to form a biofilm
216 containing a variety of microorganisms. In the ocean, bacteria act as the initial settlers, which
217 rapidly form biofilm on the surface of microorganisms, and increase the sensitivity of microbial
218 matrix to other marine organisms colonization.[17] Subsequently, eukaryotes such as fungi,
219 algae and protozoa act as secondary settlers of microplastics. The colonization of eukaryotes
220 increases the complexity of the biomembrane community structure.[42] Research shows that in
221 the Baltic Sea water at 20 °C, it only takes 10-14 weeks to form a stable biofilm on the surface
222 of 1mm PE and PS.[43]

223 3.2 Types of Microorganisms on the Surface of MPs

224 The microorganisms on MPs come from nature, but MPs have a special microbial
225 community, which is why researchers are interested in it. Compared to the organic substrate,
226 the microbial community which settles on the surface of MPs has special taxonomic
227 composition and community structure, and may show the metabolism and oxidation functions
228 of a variety of microorganisms.[44] That is mainly because that the floating life of plastic debris
229 is longer and the hydrophobic surface can promote the adsorption of bacteria and accelerate the
230 formation of biofilm. More and more research on the microbial communities colonizing the
231 marine plastic debris has repeatedly found some classes and species of bacteria, and Zettler et.
232 al put forward the term "plastisphere" for this unique habitat.[45] They characterized the
233 microbial communities on plastic marine debris in the North Atlantic using SEM and DNA
234 sequencing, and found that microbial communities on MPs are highly diverse, which are
235 distinct from surrounding surface water.

236 There have been many new studies on the specific microbial species composition through
 237 microbiological sequencing. Xu et al. applied high-throughput sequencing to investigate the
 238 successional stages of microbial communities attached to polypropylene and polyvinyl chloride
 239 MPs exposed for one year in the coastal seawater of China. The results showed that the
 240 microbial assemblage on plastic particles was mainly composed of bacterial phyla
 241 Proteobacteria and Bacteroides at the phylum level. At the class level, the dominant bacteria in
 242 PP and PVC microcellular biofilm were Gammaproteobacteria, Alphaproteobacteria, and
 243 Flavobacteria, accounting for 63.49% - 97.50% of the biofilm community as shown in Figure
 244 3.[42] In a recent review, Roager et al. analyzed bacteria colonizing the surface of marine
 245 plastic debris and concluded that Erythrobacteraceae and Rhodobacteraceae
 246 (Alphaproteobacteria), Flavobacteriaceae (Bacteroidetes), and the phylum of Cyanobacteria
 247 (such as the Phormidium genus) are the recurring groups and families often identified when
 248 comparing the taxonomic patterns. [15]

249
 250 Figure. 3 Abundance of bacteria associated with microplastics at the class level. [42]

251
 252 There is no doubt that the microbial community composition on the surface of microplastics
 253 is affected by many factors. The composition of colony on the surface of microplastics is first
 254 affected by the type of polymer, because different kinds of polymer have different
 255 hydrophobicity and additives that may be released.[46] However, some studies show that there
 256 is no significant difference in the composition of biofilm between different matrix types.[44]
 257 On the other hand, the composition of biofilm on the surface of MPs is influenced by seasons
 258 and positions, or environmental factors like temperature, salinity and inorganic nitrogen. For
 259 example, in winter, the diversity of microbial community was affected by the decrease of
 260 seawater temperature. In general, the microbial diversity level of microplastics increased with

261 the increase of exposure time, including Shannon diversity index and the number of dominant
262 microorganisms.[42] From the perspective of location, De Tender et al. summarized a large
263 number of data sets from three oceans around the world. Under different research conditions
264 and methods, the same marine area still shows similar bacterial community composition. In the
265 Atlantic and the Pacific areas, the most dominant classes were Alpha- and
266 Gammaproteobacteria, whereas in the North Sea they are Flavobacteria and
267 Gammaproteobacteria.[47]

268 At the same time, the species composition changes in the process of the aging of
269 microplastics and the development of colonized microorganisms. This process is a complex
270 process of microbial competition, niche allocation and horizontal gene transfer, induced by the
271 colonized matrix. The proliferation of specific bacteria also showed the active role of the
272 substrate as a carbon source. [48]

273 In conclusion, biofilm dominated by Gammaproteobacteria, Alphaproteobacteria, and
274 Flavobacteria will form on the surface of microplastics in a short period. Although the
275 composition of biofilm is affected by various factors, the species of colonies on the surface of
276 MPs in the main area of concern is similar. This is also the basis for the analysis of the
277 degradation potential of each bacterium in the next part.

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279 4. Discussion

280 4.1 Interaction Between Biofilm on Microplastics and Adsorbed Pollutants

281 After understanding the pollutants adsorbed on the surface of microplastics, the biofilm
282 formation process, and the species of microorganisms, we now summarize the existing
283 literature on direct degradation or adsorption of pollutants by bacteria and biofilms.

284 4.1.1 Degradation of organic pollutants

285 Several kinds of marine bacteria colonizing the surface of MPs have been reported to have
286 the potential to degrade POPs. There are a lot of Proteobacteria on the debris of marine plastics,
287 and Proteobacteria contain a large number of bacteria that are specific to the degradation of
288 pollutants.[49] One of the common bacteria, *Erythrobacteraceae*, which is widely found on the
289 surface of microplastics, is a famous group of PAH degrading bacteria. Compared with the
290 natural organic particles, this kind of bacteria is more likely to colonize on the plastic particles,
291 which may be due to its ability to use PAHs enriched by microplastics as the carbon source for
292 growth.[50] In Gammaproteobacteria, *Pseudomonas* are also highlighted by several research
293 groups[51] due to their discovery on a variety of micro plastic surfaces. But what we found is
294 even more surprising is that the species of the *Pseudomonas* genus appeared in the literature of
295 degradation of PCB, PFAS and CIP[52-54]. In the domain of bacteria, some plastic settlers
296 found more frequently on PE and PS than on glass beads and wood particles as well. Some
297 species belonging to Sphingobacteria can metabolize PAHs. [55]

298 The reason that these microorganisms can specifically degrade corresponding pollutants is
 299 that they contain genomes or plasmids that produce specific enzymes for the corresponding
 300 degradation process. Sometimes the enzyme produced by one organism can only degrade to the
 301 intermediate, and it needs another organism to continue to degrade, so a specific bacterial
 302 community is produced.[56] Based on this principle, we can think that as long as the bacteria
 303 on the surface of MPs have the corresponding genome, that is, it is a bacterial can normally
 304 express and produce the corresponding enzyme system, it has the ability to degrade the
 305 corresponding pollutants.

306 Based on the species of bacteria colonizing the surface of MPs summarized in the literature,
 307 Table 1 lists the sampling sites, the capacity of degradation of corresponding pollutants in the
 308 current literature, and the corresponding sources. It should be pointed out that the listed
 309 microbial species are accurate to the family and not comprehensive. This is only the microbial
 310 species with specific degradation ability that we can find. From this table, we can think that the
 311 microorganisms colonizing the surface of MPs have the potential to degrade POPs, which has
 312 been widely found in the global waters. But we expect more direct experiments and solid data
 313 to prove the bacteria on MPs can degrade the pollutants. Moreover, *Pseudomonas* may have the
 314 potential to degrade a variety of pollutants, including emerging pollutants, even polymers
 315 themselves.

316

317 Table 1. Bacterial species (accurate to family) colonized on the surface of microplastics,
 318 sampling locations,[15] and their corresponding pollutant degradation

Family/ Order/ Class	Sampling Site	Degradation	Resource
<i>Saprospiraceae/ Sphingobacteriales/ Sphingo-bacteriaa</i>	Yangtze Estuary, North Atlantic Ocean, North Pacific Ocean, Baltic Sea	PAHs	[55]
<i>Erythrobacteraceae/ Sphingomonadales/ Alpha-proteobacteriab</i>	North Sea, Mediterranean Sea, North Atlantic Ocean, Yangtze Estuary, Baltic Sea	PAHs	[50]
<i>Alcanivoracaceae/Oceanospirillales/ Gamma-proteobacteriab</i>	North Sea, Mediterranean Sea	PCB	[57]
<i>Pseudoaltero-monadaceae/ Alteromonadales/ Gamma-proteobacteriab</i>	North Sea, North Atlantic Ocean, Yangtze Estuary	PCB, PAFS, CIP	[52-54]
<i>Vibrionaceae/Vibrionales/ Gamma-proteobacteriab</i>	North Sea, North Atlantic Ocean	PAHs	[58]

319

320 At the same time, the common microorganisms in the marine environment also have the
 321 ability of degrading the organic pollutants enriched on the surface of microplastics. Microbial

322 communities have complex self-regulation. They not only react with carbon sources and
 323 hydrocarbons in known forms, but also react with emerging pollutants in complex ways. In one
 324 study, PFAS and other persistent pollutants were injected into different sites in the northwest
 325 Mediterranean region. The results showed that the extracellular enzyme activity of
 326 microorganisms was specifically stimulated and the community composition of
 327 microorganisms was changed after exposure to organic pollutants.[59] This supports that the
 328 microbial community on the MPs in other natural environments may react similarly after
 329 absorbing new pollutants in seawater.

330 In conclusion, for PCB, PAH and other pollutants, their stable chemical structure can only
 331 be degraded by corresponding specific microorganisms. For emerging pollutants, the natural
 332 community of a variety of microorganisms has significant physiological adaptability and
 333 decomposition potential.[56] Because of the ability of microplastics to enrich these organic
 334 pollutants, we think that MPs provide a new environment and platform for pollutant degradation.
 335 On the basis of the formation of a purposeful biofilm community, various microorganisms
 336 loaded on microplastics also undergo adaptive adjustment and further colonization.

337 4.1.2 Adsorption and removal of heavy metals

338 The biofilm on the surface of MPs can promote the accumulation of metals on the plastic
 339 particles. A study[24] determined the relationship between the growth of biofilms and
 340 particulate metal accumulation in estuarine environments within a month of particles made
 341 from particles made from different synthetic plastic polymers as well as glass microspheres as
 342 control. In the first week, the metal accumulation on the surface of glass particles was more,
 343 and one month later, the metal on the surface of LDPE and PLA exceeded the glass particles
 344 due to the appearance of biofilm. Through the correlation analysis of biofilm growth and metal
 345 accumulation, it was found that the enrichment of Ba, Cs, Ga, Fe, Ni, Rb was highly correlated
 346 with biofilm formation, while Al, K, Na, U, Cu, Pb, Co, Mn, Mg was highly correlated with
 347 the emergence of biofilm as well as polymer type[62] as shown in Figure 4.

Significant Predictor Variables of Metal Accumulation

348
 349 Figure. 4 Metal accumulation on plastic pellets positively correlated with amount of biofilm.

350 (Redrawn from [62])

351 Therefore, with the increase of residence time of MPs in water, the growth of biofilm on
352 the surface of MPs may promote the continuous accumulation of metals. It has been proved
353 that the maturity of biofilm will affect the adsorption capacity of metals. [63]

354 The metal that accumulates on the surface of the microplastics may be further used as a
355 nutrient by the cells in the biofilm, which leads to the removal of the metal from the
356 environment. Kurniawan et al. found that metals in biofilms are combined differently than
357 adsorption, and biofilm-mediated metal adsorption may be a way for biofilms to actively use
358 metals as growth factors.[60]

359 Compared with various physical and chemical methods to remove heavy metals from the
360 environment, marine microorganisms degrade and remove heavy metals without generating any
361 by-products. *Vibrio harveyi*, a common bacterium in the ocean, has been reported to have the
362 ability to enrich Cd, and its cadmium content in cells can reach 23.3mg/g[61], and the bacterium
363 family to which they belong, *Vibrionaceae*, has been reported on the surface of microplastics
364 as mentioned in Table 1. Similar bacteria are *Rhodobium marinum* and *Rhodobacter*
365 *sphaeroides*. They can remove Cu, Pb, Cd, Zn and other heavy metals from the polluted
366 environment through biosorption and biotransformation[62], and they will also grow on the
367 surface of microplastics. [15]

368 Extracellular polysaccharide produced by biofilm can effectively chelate metals. Although
369 there is no detailed study on this phenomenon, it is classified as a kind of biosorption. [62]
370 However, as EPS is produced by many bacteria in the ocean, which makes us suspect that other
371 bacteria in the sea also have the possibility of colonizing on the surface of microplastics
372 enriched with heavy metals. It has been reported that the metal adsorption of
373 exopolysaccharides produced by *Zoogloea* sp. [63], and *E. cloacea*, even a kind of unicellular
374 alga, *Chlorella* sp., are used as a non-specific biosorption agent for heavy metals such as cobalt,
375 copper and chromium.[62] Several marine bacteria highly resistant to mercury, identified as
376 *Alcaligenes faecalis*, *Bacillus pumilus*, *Bacillus* sp., *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and
377 *Brevibacterium iodinium*, have potential to detoxify Hg, Cd and Pb through putative entrapment
378 in the secreted EPS. [64] Therefore, microplastics floating in the ocean may have the ability to
379 enrich heavy metals through extracellular polymers produced by surface biofilms.

380 In conclusion, the supported biofilm may promote the interaction between microplastics
381 and heavy metals. Biofilms can adsorb heavy metals through biological enrichment and
382 biosorption by the function of EPS. Therefore, a large number of bacteria in the ocean also have
383 the possibility to adsorb heavy metals during their interaction with microplastics.

384 4.2 Analysis from the Perspective of MPs' Life Cycle in the Environment

385 After obtaining the possibility of degradation of various pollutants by biofilms on the
386 surface of microplastics, we try to apply information to the whole life cycle of microplastics to
387 think about the impact of this interaction on a longer timescale.

388 In the floating stage of the initial discharge into the water environment, the hydrophobic
389 surface of microplastics in the sea water is rapidly colonized by the initial microorganisms.[40]
390 At the same time, due to the high background concentrations of organic pollutants and metals
391 in the environment, pollutants accumulate to very high concentrations on the surface of MPs
392 within a few months. Gradually, a stable biofilm formed with MPs surface pollutants as part of
393 the carbon source.[15] After a biofilm has been formed, MPs of any kind can float in the water
394 column 1 meter below the water surface, moving with the current and being affected by natural
395 weathering.[23]

396 With the action of photooxidation, thermal oxidation and biodegradation, the surface area
397 of microplastics increases, and more oxygen-containing functional groups are exposed on the
398 surface, so the adsorption kinetics and adsorption properties change.[29] Firstly, the adsorption
399 capacity of organic pollutants and metals is further increased due to stronger capacity to sorb
400 hydrophilic compounds, and then new pollutants, such as PAFS and CIP, may be adsorbed.[30]
401 At the same time, the biofilm on MPs surface has undergone continuous succession, its
402 microbial composition has further changed to adapt to new carbon sources and carriers, and the
403 EPS produced by to form biofilm will further increase the adsorption performance.[39]

404 After additional aging, research shows that microplastics may become part of the sea snow,
405 and gradually sink into the bottom sediments of the ocean. It should be noted that the biofilm
406 of microplastics is quite different from that of other marine substrates.[65] This may be due to
407 the selection of colony structure by pollutant components on its surface. The microbial
408 concentration on the surface of the sea snow can reach 10000 times of that of the surrounding
409 sea water, and the microbial community in the sediment often inherits from the sea snow.[66]
410 Therefore, the mature degradation bacteria on the surface of microplastics may continue to play
411 a role at the end of the MPs life cycle, because there are often high concentrations of pollutants
412 in the sediments.[53]

413 Even if the micro-organisms on the surface of the micro plastics cannot degrade all the
414 attached pollutants, the promotion of the microplastics on the biogeochemical cycle of the
415 adsorbed pollutants to made them more toxic to aquatic organisms through concentration and
416 movement is also small. There have been models[67] and experimental studies[68] to analyze
417 the impact of microplastics as a carrier of POPs on aquatic organisms such as fish, benthos and
418 seagulls. The results show that from the perspective of environmental risk assessment, while
419 large amounts of plastic have been deposited into the global oceans, the actual concentration of
420 MPs in seawater is still comparably low. The desorption of the organic pollutants adsorbed on
421 its surface needs certain conditions, its auxiliary carrier effect on POPs can almost be ignored.
422 Some studies have shown that the bioavailability of POPs and Cu decreased after adsorbed on
423 microplastics, which may be caused by the biofilm on their surface. Because the degradation
424 rate cannot be determined, we can also regard microplastics and biofilm as containers for
425 pollutant storage and degradation, especially when they sink to the sediment after accumulating
426 lots of pollutants.

427 4.3 Could Microplastics Clean Our Ocean?

428 Based on the above information and analysis, we now try to summarize the possibility of
429 microbial degradation of adsorbed organic pollutants and heavy metals on the surface of MPs
430 in the marine environment. And answer the questions raised in the beginning: could MPs serve
431 as platforms for specific microbial community degradation of enriched harmful pollutants and
432 could they play roles in cleaning the ocean?

433 First of all, from the perspective of spatial distribution, the main distribution sites and
434 emission paths of microplastics and marine pollutants are highly coincident. In Section 2, we
435 highlighted the global distribution of pollutants adsorbed by microplastics. The highest
436 concentration of pollutants is detected in the estuaries of large coastal cities in developing
437 countries. [26] This is because microplastics and organic pollutants, as well as heavy metal
438 pollution sources and emission paths are concentrated human aggregation areas. After organic
439 pollutant are released through industrial pollution sources, they enter the marine environment
440 mainly through wastewater discharge.[27] For microplastics, the primary microparticles enter
441 the ocean mainly through the urban wastewater discharge through the estuary area, and the
442 secondary MPs are produced by a large number of bigger pieces of plastic discharged from the
443 land.[4] For heavy metals, they enter the water from fishing and industrial activities at the
444 mouth of the river.[35] Therefore, microplastics are in frequent contact with these pollutants
445 and adsorb in areas with high concentration of marine pollutants. It is expected that attachment
446 to particles and biofilm formation to be comparable in each of regions with high pollutant
447 concentration, so we can think that the process of biofilm formation is basically the same.

448 Second, from the point of view of species distribution, the microorganisms colonizing the
449 surface of MPs have the potential to degrade the pollutants adsorbed on the surface of MPs.
450 Several families of microorganisms colonizing MPs have been reported to have the ability to
451 degrade PAH and PCB, [50] and have strong capacity for the degradation of emerging pollutants.
452 Because microplastics provide a new carrier of high concentration organic pollutants, the
453 surface of microplastics will continuously produce mature microbial groups which are more
454 suitable for degradation and utilization of carbon sources in the complex process of marine
455 microbial colonization.[42] For heavy metals, the formation of biofilms changes the physical
456 and chemical properties of the surface of microplastics, which can promote the accumulation
457 of various metals on its surface.[62] At the same time, specific bacteria can absorb and utilize
458 the corresponding heavy metals, and the EPS produced by biofilm can further chelate heavy
459 metals. [62] Because heavy metals are only taken up by microbes and accumulate in biofilms
460 but cannot be further degraded, MP may become a storage for highly concentrated heavy
461 metals. [24]

462 Third, from the perspective of MPs' life cycle, with the continuous aging of microplastics,
463 the physical and chemical properties of its surface change, making it even more likely to
464 become a place where bacteria interact with pollutants.[30] Microplastics can float in the ocean

465 for decades.[69] Weathering and aging increase the surface area and the capacity to bind more
466 hydrophilic pollutants, and the biofilm on the surface has also undergone succession and change.
467 It can be considered that composition of pollutants adsorbed to MP particles are changing with
468 time, but the biofilm also changes with the change of pollutants on the surface, so there is
469 potential of continuous degradation.

470 Therefore, we concluded that microplastics could constitute an ideal platform for marine
471 microorganisms to degrade and store high concentration pollutants. At present, due to the
472 comparably low concentration of microplastics in the ocean, degradation of pollutants by
473 microbes on MP particles only has a small effect on the total amount of these pollutants. Of
474 course, before a large number of microplastics are put into the clean Ocean, we need further
475 experiments to evaluate the actual degradation ability of microorganisms for pollutants
476 adsorbed to the surface of microplastics, as well as the potential risks of microplastics as carriers
477 of pollutants and microorganisms after being ingested by marine organisms.

478

479 **5 Conclusion and Outlook**

480 In summary, we reviewed what pollutants adsorbed to the surface of microplastics, the
481 biofilm formation process and the types of microorganisms forming these biofilms. And the
482 relevant literature on the degradation of pollutants by these microorganisms are examined. We
483 think that in the life cycle of microplastics, it may function as a carrier of a variety of toxic
484 pollutants, and attract a special biofilm that degrades and transforms these pollutants.

485 In the course of investigation, we found that there are few literature about the interaction
486 between biofilm and surface adsorbed pollutants on microplastics, and most of them have no
487 quantitative data. Therefore, in the future research, we may focus more on whether MP
488 associated bacteria can degrade the adsorbed pollutants. Experiments over whether the carbon
489 source of biofilm growth on the surface of microplastics comes from the pollutants on its
490 surface can be further explored to make a more accurate assessment of microplastics and the
491 toxic pollutants it adsorbs in the whole life cycle. For example, how does the pollutant
492 concentration on particles change over time if there is a biofilm or if there is no biofilm. And
493 MPs eventually end up in the sediment where POPs concentration are higher as well, so the
494 degradation of pollutants by biofilm on the surface of microplastics brought to the sediments
495 may be further studied, where the conditions are a bit different. In order to understand the
496 impact of microplastics on the biogeochemical cycle of pollutants, we still have a long way to
497 go.

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503 **References**

- 504 1. UNEP, *Marine plastic debris and microplastics - Global lessons and research to inspire action*
505 *and guide policy change*. 2016, United Nation Environment Programme: Nairobi.
- 506 2. Jambeck, J.R., et al., *Plastic waste inputs from land into the ocean*. *Science*, 2015. **347**(6223):
507 p. 768.
- 508 3. Thompson, R.C., et al., *Lost at Sea: Where Is All the Plastic?* *Science*, 2004. **304**(5672): p. 838.
- 509 4. Cole, M., et al., *Microplastics as contaminants in the marine environment: A review*. *Marine*
510 *Pollution Bulletin*, 2011. **62**(12): p. 2588-2597.
- 511 5. Zarfl, C. and M. Matthies, *Are marine plastic particles transport vectors for organic pollutants*
512 *to the Arctic?* *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 2010. **60**(10): p. 1810-1814.
- 513 6. Lusher, A.L., et al., *Microplastics in Arctic polar waters: the first reported values of particles*
514 *in surface and sub-surface samples*. *Scientific Reports*, 2015. **5**(1): p. 14947.
- 515 7. Pan, Z., et al., *Microplastics in the Northwestern Pacific: Abundance, distribution, and*
516 *characteristics*. *Science of The Total Environment*, 2019. **650**: p. 1913-1922.
- 517 8. Wang, F., F. Wang, and E.Y. Zeng, *Chapter 7 - Sorption of Toxic Chemicals on Microplastics,*
518 *in Microplastic Contamination in Aquatic Environments*, E.Y. Zeng, Editor. 2018, Elsevier. p.
519 225-247.
- 520 9. Heinrich, P. and T. Braunbeck, *Bioavailability of microplastic-bound pollutants in vitro: The*
521 *role of adsorbate lipophilicity and surfactants*. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part*
522 *C: Toxicology & Pharmacology*, 2019. **221**: p. 59-67.
- 523 10. Ziccardi, L.M., et al., *Microplastics as vectors for bioaccumulation of hydrophobic organic*
524 *chemicals in the marine environment: A state-of-the-science review*. *Environmental Toxicology*
525 *and Chemistry*, 2016. **35**(7): p. 1667-1676.
- 526 11. Caruso, G., *Microplastics as vectors of contaminants*. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 2019. **146**: p.
527 921-924.
- 528 12. Diepens, N.J. and A.A. Koelmans, *Accumulation of Plastic Debris and Associated*
529 *Contaminants in Aquatic Food Webs*. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 2018. **52**(15): p.
530 8510-8520.
- 531 13. Hodson, M.E., et al., *Plastic Bag Derived-Microplastics as a Vector for Metal Exposure in*
532 *Terrestrial Invertebrates*. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 2017. **51**(8): p. 4714-4721.
- 533 14. Carpenter, E.J., et al., *Polystyrene Spherules in Coastal Waters*. *Science*, 1972. **178**(4062): p.
534 749.
- 535 15. Roager, L. and E.C. Sonnenschein, *Bacterial Candidates for Colonization and Degradation of*
536 *Marine Plastic Debris*. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 2019. **53**(20): p. 11636-11643.
- 537 16. Vert, M., et al., *Terminology for biorelated polymers and applications (IUPAC*
538 *Recommendations 2012)*, in *Pure and Applied Chemistry*. 2012. p. 377.
- 539 17. Lobelle, D. and M. Cunliffe, *Early microbial biofilm formation on marine plastic debris*. *Marine*
540 *Pollution Bulletin*, 2011. **62**(1): p. 197-200.
- 541 18. Besseling, E., et al., *Effects of Microplastic on Fitness and PCB Bioaccumulation by the*
542 *Lugworm Arenicola marina (L.)*. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 2013. **47**(1): p. 593-
543 600.
- 544 19. Grigorakis, S. and K.G. Drouillard, *Effect of Microplastic Amendment to Food on Diet*
545 *Assimilation Efficiencies of PCBs by Fish*. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 2018. **52**(18):

- 546 p. 10796-10802.
- 547 20. Herzke, D., et al., *Negligible Impact of Ingested Microplastics on Tissue Concentrations of*
548 *Persistent Organic Pollutants in Northern Fulmars off Coastal Norway*. Environmental Science
549 & Technology, 2016. **50**(4): p. 1924-1933.
- 550 21. Rodrigues, J.P., et al., *Significance of interactions between microplastics and POPs in the*
551 *marine environment: A critical overview*. TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry, 2019. **111**: p.
552 252-260.
- 553 22. Papale, M., et al., *Enrichment, isolation and biodegradation potential of psychrotolerant*
554 *polychlorinated-biphenyl degrading bacteria from the Kongsfjorden (Svalbard Islands, High*
555 *Arctic Norway)*. Marine Pollution Bulletin, 2017. **114**(2): p. 849-859.
- 556 23. Dhar, K., et al., *Anaerobic Microbial Degradation of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons: A*
557 *Comprehensive Review*, in *Reviews of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology Volume*
558 *251*, P. de Voogt, Editor. 2020, Springer International Publishing: Cham. p. 25-108.
- 559 24. Richard, H., et al., *Biofilm facilitates metal accumulation onto microplastics in estuarine waters*.
560 *Science of The Total Environment*, 2019. **683**: p. 600-608.
- 561 25. Velzeboer, I., C.J.A.F. Kwadijk, and A.A. Koelmans, *Strong Sorption of PCBs to Nanoplastics,*
562 *Microplastics, Carbon Nanotubes, and Fullerenes*. Environmental Science & Technology, 2014.
563 **48**(9): p. 4869-4876.
- 564 26. Guo, X. and J. Wang, *The chemical behaviors of microplastics in marine environment: A review*.
565 *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 2019. **142**: p. 1-14.
- 566 27. Beyer, A. and M. Biziuk, *Environmental Fate and Global Distribution of Polychlorinated*
567 *Biphenyls*, in *Reviews of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology Vol 201*, D.M. Whitacre,
568 Editor. 2009, Springer US: Boston, MA. p. 137-158.
- 569 28. Lohmann, R. and J. Dachs, *Chapter 15 - Polychlorinated Biphenyls in the Global Ocean*, in
570 *World Seas: an Environmental Evaluation (Second Edition)*, C. Sheppard, Editor. 2019,
571 Academic Press. p. 269-282.
- 572 29. Llorca, M., et al., *Adsorption of perfluoroalkyl substances on microplastics under environmental*
573 *conditions*. Environmental Pollution, 2018. **235**: p. 680-691.
- 574 30. Liu, G., et al., *Sorption behavior and mechanism of hydrophilic organic chemicals to virgin and*
575 *aged microplastics in freshwater and seawater*. Environmental Pollution, 2019. **246**: p. 26-33.
- 576 31. Wang, M., et al., *Ecological risk assessment to marine organisms induced by heavy metals in*
577 *China's coastal waters*. Marine Pollution Bulletin, 2018. **126**: p. 349-356.
- 578 32. Rochman, C.M., B.T. Hentschel, and S.J. Teh, *Long-Term Sorption of Metals Is Similar among*
579 *Plastic Types: Implications for Plastic Debris in Aquatic Environments*. PLOS ONE, 2014. **9**(1):
580 p. e85433.
- 581 33. Brennecke, D., et al., *Microplastics as vector for heavy metal contamination from the marine*
582 *environment*. Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science, 2016. **178**: p. 189-195.
- 583 34. Holmes, L.A., A. Turner, and R.C. Thompson, *Adsorption of trace metals to plastic resin pellets*
584 *in the marine environment*. Environmental Pollution, 2012. **160**: p. 42-48.
- 585 35. Wang, Q., et al., *The adsorption behavior of metals in aqueous solution by microplastics effected*
586 *by UV radiation*. Journal of Environmental Sciences, 2020. **87**: p. 272-280.
- 587 36. Godoy, V., et al., *The potential of microplastics as carriers of metals*. Environmental Pollution,
588 2019. **255**: p. 113363.
- 589 37. Galgani, L., et al., *Polystyrene microplastics increase microbial release of marine*

- 590 *Chromophoric Dissolved Organic Matter in microcosm experiments*. Scientific Reports, 2018.
591 **8**(1): p. 14635.
- 592 38. Paerl, H.W., *Microbial attachment to particles in marine and freshwater ecosystems*. Microbial
593 Ecology, 1975. **2**(1): p. 73-83.
- 594 39. Donlan, R.M., *Biofilms: microbial life on surfaces*. Emerging infectious diseases, 2002. **8**(9): p.
595 881-890.
- 596 40. Rummel, C.D., et al., *Impacts of Biofilm Formation on the Fate and Potential Effects of*
597 *Microplastic in the Aquatic Environment*. Environmental Science & Technology Letters, 2017.
598 **4**(7): p. 258-267.
- 599 41. Flemming, H.-C. and J. Wingender, *The biofilm matrix*. Nature Reviews Microbiology, 2010.
600 **8**(9): p. 623-633.
- 601 42. Xu, X., et al., *Marine microplastic-associated bacterial community succession in response to*
602 *geography, exposure time, and plastic type in China's coastal seawaters*. Marine Pollution
603 Bulletin, 2019. **145**: p. 278-286.
- 604 43. Kaiser, D., N. Kowalski, and J.J. Waniek, *Effects of biofouling on the sinking behavior of*
605 *microplastics*. Environmental Research Letters, 2017. **12**(12): p. 124003.
- 606 44. Miao, L., et al., *Distinct community structure and microbial functions of biofilms colonizing*
607 *microplastics*. Science of The Total Environment, 2019. **650**: p. 2395-2402.
- 608 45. Zettler, E.R., T.J. Mincer, and L.A. Amaral-Zettler, *Life in the "Plastisphere": Microbial*
609 *Communities on Plastic Marine Debris*. Environmental Science & Technology, 2013. **47**(13):
610 p. 7137-7146.
- 611 46. Wang, J., et al., *The behaviors of microplastics in the marine environment*. Marine
612 Environmental Research, 2016. **113**: p. 7-17.
- 613 47. De Tender, C., et al., *A review of microscopy and comparative molecular-based methods to*
614 *characterize "Plastisphere" communities*. Analytical Methods, 2017. **9**(14): p. 2132-2143.
- 615 48. Sørensen, S.J., et al., *Studying plasmid horizontal transfer in situ: a critical review*. Nature
616 Reviews Microbiology, 2005. **3**(9): p. 700-710.
- 617 49. Vila, J., M. Tauler, and M. Grifoll, *Bacterial PAH degradation in marine and terrestrial habitats*.
618 Current Opinion in Biotechnology, 2015. **33**: p. 95-102.
- 619 50. Zhuang, L., et al., *Erythrobacter atlanticus sp. nov., a bacterium from ocean sediment able to*
620 *degrade polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons*. International Journal of Systematic and
621 Evolutionary Microbiology, 2015. **65**(10): p. 3714-3719.
- 622 51. Oberbeckmann, S., M.G.J. Löder, and M. Labrenz, *Marine microplastic-associated biofilms –*
623 *a review*. Environmental Chemistry, 2015. **12**(5): p. 551-562.
- 624 52. Master, E.R. and W.W. Mohn, *Psychrotolerant bacteria isolated from Arctic soil that degrade*
625 *polychlorinated biphenyls at low temperatures*. Applied and Environmental Microbiology, 1998.
626 **64**(12): p. 4823-4829.
- 627 53. Liu, J. and S. Mejia Avendaño, *Microbial degradation of polyfluoroalkyl chemicals in the*
628 *environment: A review*. Environment International, 2013. **61**: p. 98-114.
- 629 54. Näslund, J., J.E. Hedman, and C. Agestrand, *Effects of the antibiotic ciprofloxacin on the*
630 *bacterial community structure and degradation of pyrene in marine sediment*. Aquatic
631 Toxicology, 2008. **90**(3): p. 223-227.
- 632 55. Leys, N.M.E.J., et al., *Occurrence and Phylogenetic Diversity of*
633 *Sphingomonas Strains in Soils Contaminated with Polycyclic Aromatic*

- 634 *Hydrocarbons*. Applied and Environmental Microbiology, 2004. **70**(4): p. 1944.
- 635 56. Chakraborty, J. and S. Das, *Molecular perspectives and recent advances in microbial*
636 *remediation of persistent organic pollutants*. Environmental Science and Pollution Research,
637 2016. **23**(17): p. 16883-16903.
- 638 57. Lambo, A.J. and T.R. Patel, *Biodegradation of polychlorinated biphenyls in Aroclor 1232 and*
639 *production of metabolites from 2,4,4'-trichlorobiphenyl at low temperature by psychrotolerant*
640 *Hydrogenophaga sp. strain IA3-A*. Journal of Applied Microbiology, 2007. **102**(5): p. 1318-
641 1329.
- 642 58. Hedlund, B.P. and J.T. Staley, *Vibrio cyclotrophicus sp. nov., a polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon*
643 *(PAH)-degrading marine bacterium*. International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary
644 Microbiology, 2001. **51**(1): p. 61-66.
- 645 59. Cerro-Gálvez, E., et al., *Modulation of microbial growth and enzymatic activities in the marine*
646 *environment due to exposure to organic contaminants of emerging concern and hydrocarbons*.
647 Science of The Total Environment, 2019. **678**: p. 486-498.
- 648 60. Kurniawan, A., et al., *Analysis of the Ion Adsorption–Desorption Characteristics of*
649 *Biofilm Matrices*. Microbes and Environments, 2012. **27**(4): p. 399-406.
- 650 61. Dash, H.R., et al., *Marine bacteria: potential candidates for enhanced bioremediation*. Applied
651 Microbiology and Biotechnology, 2013. **97**(2): p. 561-571.
- 652 62. Iyer, A., K. Mody, and B. Jha, *Biosorption of heavy metals by a marine bacterium*. Marine
653 Pollution Bulletin, 2005. **50**(3): p. 340-343.
- 654 63. Kong, J.Y., et al., *Utilization of a cell-bound polysaccharide produced by the marine bacterium*
655 *Zoogloea sp.: new biomaterial for metal adsorption and enzyme immobilization*. Journal of
656 Marine Biotechnology, 1998. **6**(2): p. 99-103.
- 657 64. De, J., A. Sarkar, and N. Ramaiah, *Bioremediation of toxic substances by mercury resistant*
658 *marine bacteria*. Ecotoxicology, 2006. **15**(4): p. 385-389.
- 659 65. Yao, P., et al., *A review of microplastics in sediments: Spatial and temporal occurrences,*
660 *biological effects, and analytic methods*. Quaternary International, 2019. **519**: p. 274-281.
- 661 66. Galloway, T.S., M. Cole, and C. Lewis, *Interactions of microplastic debris throughout the*
662 *marine ecosystem*. Nature Ecology & Evolution, 2017. **1**(5): p. 0116.
- 663 67. Koelmans, A.A., et al., *Plastic as a Carrier of POPs to Aquatic Organisms: A Model Analysis*.
664 Environmental Science & Technology, 2013. **47**(14): p. 7812-7820.
- 665 68. Koelmans, A.A., et al., *Microplastic as a Vector for Chemicals in the Aquatic Environment:*
666 *Critical Review and Model-Supported Reinterpretation of Empirical Studies*. Environmental
667 Science & Technology, 2016. **50**(7): p. 3315-3326.
- 668 69. Xu, S., et al., *Microplastics in aquatic environments: Occurrence, accumulation, and biological*
669 *effects*. Science of The Total Environment, 2020. **703**: p. 134699.
- 670